

eKitabu

Begin with Books

Final Project Report

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Acknowledgement

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1.0 Executive Summary

eKitabu began work under the All Children Reading: A Grand Challenge for Development (ACR GCD) Begin With Books (BWB) award in April 2022. With our Begin With Books award, eKitabu developed accessible early grade reading materials in underserved languages of Malawi: Citumbuka, Malawian Sign Language (MSL), Chichewa, Ciyawo and Ellomwe. These materials are a mix of new titles developed with Malawian authors and in collaboration with Malawians with disabilities, including members of the Malawi National Association of the Deaf (MANAD) that positively represented children and family members with disabilities, and adaptations of existing titles, including titles from the Global Digital Library for a total of 282 titles adapted or developed and delivered in accessible formats, and 1,286 unique versions across specific formats prioritized for accessibility including EPUB, MSL video, human-narrated audio, electronic braille and cropped and uncropped PDFs.

This report provides details of the project milestones and deliverables, impact, lessons learned and next steps. **eKitabu sincerely and heartily thanks All Children Reading: A Grand Challenge for Development for their constant communication, support and collaboration for mutual success throughout the project.** We would especially like to acknowledge the ongoing support - formal and informal - we received from fellow awardees and from RIT through the Sign Language Storybook Cohort (SLSC) community via Slack and our topical web conferences. The BWB Minimum and Gold Standards for Sign Language Video Storybooks provided solid guidance for eKitabu's team and DPO partners.

eKitabu

<p>Kambuzi Kanga Chich... Bukheye Mulongo Christop...</p>					
<p>Zochita Ng'ombe Yoziz... Danielle Bruckert</p>					

BWB accessible books in eKitabu Cloud Reader

1.1 Accessible Titles Produced under Begin With Books

Approach / Track	Language	Source of Books	Level 1a	Level 1b	Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3	Total
COVID and Health/Hygiene Book Set	Citumbuka, Ciyawo, Lomwe, English	Creative Commons content		4		4	4	12
Adapting books	Citumbuka	GDL	50	50	50	50		200
Creating new books, including protagonists representing children and family members with disabilities	Citumbuka	New books created by eKitabu BWB team and edited by Helen Patuck with some books edited and illustrated by colleagues in MANAD	15			5		20
Sign Language	Malawian Sign Language (MSL) with Chichewa and Citumbuka text	Books selected from Approach 1 set for level and adaptability into MSL	25	25				50
Total			90	79	50	59	4	282

1.2 Titles Delivered by Language

Languages	Number of Titles
Written Citumbuka	223
Written Ciyawo	3
Written Ellomwe	3
Malawian Sign Language Video with Tumbuka text	10
Malawian Sign Language Video with Chichewa text	40
English (COVID books)	3

1.3 Accessible Digital Content Formats (unique files) delivered

Milestone	PDF		EPUB			E-braille	Total
	<i>without crop marks</i>	<i>with crop marks</i>	<i>EPUB 3</i>	<i>with human narration</i>	<i>with MSL video embedded</i>		
Milestone 2	12	12	12				36
Milestone 3	65	65	65	65		65	325
Milestone 4	155	155	155	155		155	775
Milestone 5	25	25			25		75
Milestone 7	25	25			25		75
Total	282	282	232	220	50	220	1,286

Funding from ACR has enabled us to deliver storybooks in underserved languages of Malawi and to bring accessible digital content, for the first time, in Malawian Sign Language. ACR’s support has further deepened and informed eKitabu’s commitment to advancing accessibility in all aspects of our work, including advocacy with the government. Accessibility is a core, guiding principle in all we do: digitizing educational materials, distributing digital content, developing open source e-reading software and tools, and delivering programs that engage and build capacity with learners, teachers, parents, caregivers, publishers and government stakeholders in education.

2.0 Project Deliverables

Through the two-year project, we:

- Delivered accessible early grade readers in underserved languages of Malawi: a total of 282 unique titles and 1,286 unique versions, including 50 titles with Malawian Sign Language video, 40 with Chichewa captions, 10 with Tumbuka captions, 223 titles in Citumbuka, 3 titles in Ellomwe, 3 titles in Ciyawo, and 3 titles in English, approved by ACR and submitted to the Global Digital Library (GDL).
- Developed 20 new early grade readers with Malawian authors, illustrators from MANAD, and edited by Helen Patuck to incorporate social and emotional learning (SEL) activities and characters that are representative of the wide diversity of Malawian readers.
- Held an Accessible Digital Content Workshop from 24th - 27th May 2022 in Blantyre, Malawi. It was attended by over 70 content developers representing key stakeholders in education including the Ministry of Education (DQAS, DSNE, MIE), USAID, publishers, Organizations of Persons with Disabilities, Development Aid of People to People (DAPP) and ACR. Adapted and released an open source Accessible EPUB Toolkit for Malawi at toolkit.ekitabu.com.
- Engaged and built capacity with Malawi Ministry of Education (MOE) officials and Malawian organizations of persons with disabilities (OPD) in developing accessible digital content.
- In collaboration with Malawi National Association of the Deaf (MANAD), developed an [MSL Early Grade Vocabulary Guide](#) that currently has 493 MSL signs with videos with audio in Citumbuka, Chichewa, and English including MSL videos developed under USAID's REFAM activity in collaboration with MANAD..
- Visited one Resource Center for children with disabilities in a mainstream school, where we provided and loaded devices with accessible digital content (ebraille), as well as two special schools for the deaf, observed utilization of content in classrooms and gathered feedback on the content developed from learners and teachers:
 - Mountain View School for the Deaf
 - Makande Resource Center for the Blind
 - Mua School for the Deaf

2.1 Summary of Milestones

Milestone #	Description of Deliverable
Milestone 1	Successful execution of prize award with World Vision for eKitabu's Open Books Malawi Begin with Books project. Contract executed.
Milestone 2	Completion of 12 Covid-19/health/hygiene adapted books for the GDL in accessible EPUB, 3 titles in 4 languages: Citumbuka, Ciyawo, Ellomwe, and English. 12 Covid-19 books produced in accessible format: 3 titles in 4 languages; Citumbuka, Ciyawo, Ellomwe, and English.

Covid-19 books developed to accessible formats

Milestone 3

Completion of **60** adapted Citumbuka books (3 sets of 20) and **5** new books that are quality assured, technically reviewed, correctly branded and leveled and transferred to GDL.

60 early grade titles in Citumbuka developed in accessible formats. Each title was produced in accessible EPUB 3.0 with and without human narrated audio, e-braille (.brf), and print-ready PDF. Total of **325** files.

5 new books developed with social emotional learning activities and/or featuring children with disabilities as protagonists.

eKitabu

Amama wakupereka masayini na mawoko ghawo.
Wakuti, “gezani mu mawoko na kulya.”
Nkhuwalongola maji wanyane kuti wageze mu mawoko.
Mbwenu nkhuqipemphelera cakulya.

6

An EPUB 3 with human narrated audio in Citumbuka highlighting text as the audio plays

Milestone 4

Completion of remaining **140** adapted Citumbuka books and additional **15** new books for a total of **200** Citumbuka (50 per level) and **20** new books (15 Level 1a and 5 Level 3) with Citumbuka text, image descriptions in English and Citumbuka, human narrated Citumbuka audio, English text, and English renditions in e-braille that are quality assured, technically reviewed, correctly branded and leveled and transferred to GDL.

140 adapted Citumbuka books, **15** new books in accessible EPUB. **155** books with human narrations approved by ACRI-Submitted 220 e-braille materials to Malawi Union of the Blind (MUB) for loading on 253 orbit readers distributed in schools. Loaded on 12 orbit readers at Makande Resource Centre.

Mercy Kirui from eKitabu with support from WVM loading e-braille materials on SD cards for access on the Orbit readers.

	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Begin with Books catalog on eKitabu App</i></p>
<p>Milestone 5</p>	<p>25 MSL books produced: 10 with Citumbuka audio and captions, 15 with Chichewa audio and captions. . which are quality assured, technically reviewed, correctly branded and leveled and transferred to GDL.</p> <p>eKitabu Studio KSL went to Malawi to provide Sign Language Video Production support to MANAD in Mponela in 2021 Here is the link to the full report.</p>

eKitabu supporting MANAD to produce MSL early grade storybooks in Lilongwe

Early grade storybook with MSL video embedded

Milestone 6

Development of 1 accessible EPUB toolkit for local content developers and publishers to use in developing their own new titles that are born accessible, and hosting of 1 accessible EPUB workshop for stakeholders.

As our work developed on this milestone, we were able to directly contribute to, and benefit from, a concurrent GBAIA project in Malawi funded by USAID. ACR facilitated eKitabu's July 2021 meeting with the USAID Malawi team, led by Education Office Director Christine Veverka and her team: Ramsey Sosola, Matt Maroon and Odala Banda. This meeting led to a direct request by Christine Veverka that we engage with GBAIA. eKitabu's Mercy Kuriui presented at GBAIA's conference in March 2021, and many of the publishers, authors and illustrators developing new titles for

eKitabu's BWB project were commissioned by GBAIA to contribute the 15 new titles developed under their project.

1 Accessible Digital Content Development Workshop held in Blantyre, Malawi, **5** draft EPUBs developed by participants during the workshop, **50** content developers trained. Accessible EPUB Toolkit developed and launched online at <https://toolkit.ekitabu.com> with a step-by-step guide to develop accessible EPUBs.

Step-by-Step Guide

- 01 Learn It**
Knowledge and skill of Epub Anatomy. Install of software and tools.
- 02 Design It**
Print books are designed with accessibility features in mind.
- 03 Digitize It**
Start from paper, scan the images and text. Extract text and images from PDF.
- 04 Download It**
Download the template for readers and reference sheets for images.
- 05 Describe It**
Type out the image descriptions for the images for Text to Speech functionality.
- 06 Epub It**
Create EPUB from base template you downloaded in download it step.
- 07 Include It**
Include Image descriptions and videos for accessibility.
- 08 Check It**
Validate the EPUB on daisy ace and Epub checker for any errors.
- 09 Test It**
Test it on readers and with your users then iterate.
- 10 Enhance It**
Adding videos, audio synchronization, open dyslexic fonts to enhance the EPUB.

A step-by-step guide to develop accessible EPUB in the Accessible EPUB Toolkit for Malawi

Our overall workshop objectives were to:

- Collaborate across the public and private sector to advance inclusive & equitable quality education—leaving no one behind.
- Share guidelines, tools and resources to develop “born accessible” content applying Universal Design for Learning principles.
- Build skills & relationships to grow a more sustainable Malawian publishing ecosystem.

[Here is the link](#) to the full final report.

Participants of the Accessible Digital Content Workshop held in Blantyre in May

Milestone 7

25 remaining adapted Citumbuka/Chichewa captioned books into MSL video storybooks all of which are quality assured, technically reviewed, correctly branded and leveled and transferred to the GDL. Developed and launched 1 MSL Early Grade Vocabulary Guide website documenting 493 signs at msl-vocabulary.ekitabu.com.

MSL Early Grade Vocabulary Guide website

Milestone 8

Submission of final report inclusive of project deliverables, lessons learned, photos and next steps.

Report submitted.

2.2 Stakeholder engagement highlights

Teachers

Teachers at Mua School for the Deaf interacting with the MSL early grade Vocabulary Guide

Government

Mrs. Lucy Magagula, Directorate of Special Needs Education (DSNE) Deputy Director, officiating at the Accessible Digital Content Workshop

Learners

Learners at Mountain View School for the Deaf interacting with MSL early grade story books with Sekerani Kufanikwa of MANAD

Organizations of Persons with Disabilities (OPD)

OPDs roundtable discussions during Accessible Digital Content workshop held at Blantyre in May

Publishers & Stakeholders

MOE, USAID & publishers during the GBAIA workshop at Malawi Sun Hotel, Blantyre

MoE, Publishers, OPDs participating during the Accessible Digital Content Development Workshop in May at Malawi Sun Hotel, Blantyre

Students at Makande Resource Centre reading storybooks loaded on the Orbit Reader

2.2 School Visit and User Feedback sessions

According to Sekerani Kufakwina from MANAD, the Malawian Sign Language (MSL) storybooks are:

- First of their kind: the first MSL video storybooks that children who are deaf and hard of hearing in Malawi are accessing.
- A great opportunity to learn new ways to package learning materials for children who are deaf or hard of hearing.
- Proven as a best practice intervention to address limited language acquisition and vocabulary learning among Deaf children.
- Very promising to improve literacy and cognitive capabilities of Deaf children through being accessible in a natural language they can use and understand.
- Are able to promote a reading culture in Malawi, increasing Deaf learners' motivation to read and including Deaf children on the journey to lifelong learning.
- A concrete and valuable resource to increase vocabulary knowledge among both teachers and children. The videos show the MSL signs and the corresponding glossary words, including the finger spelling, to make the connection between MSL signs and spoken and written language.

School	Observations and feedback	Photos
Mountain View School for Deaf Children	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Children stay in Grade 1 for 5 years before progressing to the next grade ● No ECD program ● All teachers are hearing ● Need support to properly assess learning progress of deaf learners both through regular instruction and new interventions ● 16 teachers, 5 teachers trained in MSL, 11 teachers with standard teacher training college 	

- “Total Communication¹” is used
- Learners often teach their teachers MSL
- Children struggled to answer comprehension questions from MSL storybooks

Sekerani Kufakwina of MANAD engaging the children in reading MSL storybooks

Group photo at Mountain View School for the Deaf with World Vision colleagues

¹ Total communication is a method for educating children with hearing loss that incorporates all means of communication including formal signs, natural gestures, fingerspelling, body language, listening, lipreading and speech; however, how it is often implemented in the classroom is with a focus on the spoken language as opposed to the sign language. Typically, the sign language is compromised and the learner does not receive full access to the learning material. Total communication is strongly criticized by the World Federation of the Deaf (<https://wfdeaf.org/our-work/human-rights-of-the-deaf/>) and the Deaf community broadly as it focuses on the use of written/spoken language instead of providing learning materials in sign language, a fully accessible, natural language.

**Makande Resource Centre
for the Blind**

- All ages of learners are together in one classroom
- The sighted teachers can read braille visually, but cannot read it tactilely
- Older children still had difficulty reading basic stories in braille
- The resource center is a segregated classroom in a mainstream school

A blind learner at Makande Resource Centre reading a storybook loaded on the Orbit Reader

Mua School for the Deaf

About the School:

- Sister school of Mountain View School for Deaf Children
- Preschool has 4 classes
- Main school has Standard 1 - 8
- Total enrolment 198, most are Deaf, some are hard of hearing
- Staff: 10 hearing and 2 deaf teachers. 3 female teachers, 9 male teachers; of the deaf teachers, 1 is female and 1 is male
- 1 auxiliary teacher to provide supplementary support in the school.
- Boarding school
- Learners are assisted by Catholic nurses
- They have a computer room, but most of the desktop computers are not functional

Teachers:

- 8 teachers attended the training, 2 of the teachers were persons who are deaf.
- They all interacted with the MSL early Grade Vocabulary Guide website
- Some could not access the Guide from their phones as their browsers were very slow due to low phone memory
- They appreciated the product as it will help them learn and practice MSL
- They have internet access in the school, but it's not reliable and it's limited to a certain radius
- Requested an offline version of the MSL

Teachers at Mua School for the Deaf interacting with MSL Early Grade Vocabulary Guide Website

Learners at Mua School for the Deaf interacting with MSL Early Grade Vocabulary Guide Website

	<p>Vocabulary Guide. eKitabu Malawi team is currently investigating the best format for an offline version based on device availability.</p> <p>Learners:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● 10 students from Standard 6 - 8 attended the training, all were Deaf● Sekerani took them through the MSL early grade Vocabulary Guide website and storybooks through the eKitabu App on the projector screen● The learners were excited about the product; it was the first time they were interacting with MSL videos in early grade stories● They asked for an upper grade version of the Vocabulary Guide, although they said this version will still be helpful to them	
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3.0 Challenges, Recommendations, and Lessons Learned during Begin With Books

In the table, below, we describe challenges encountered during the project and pair them with recommendations and lessons learned.

Challenge	Recommendation and/or Lesson Learned
Overall challenges impacting project timeline	
<p>COVID-19: COVID disruptions affected the timeline of the project immediately as we started in April 2020. Coordinating and establishing working relationships with colleagues in Malawi was particularly difficult during project startup. Regular power outages and poor internet connectivity made remote work very difficult for our Malawian team members and colleagues, and travel was not possible at that time as the country was in lockdown.</p> <p>The major impact of starting remotely was our ability to engage government stakeholders, especially the Ministry of Education Department of Special Needs Education (DSNE) and Malawi Institute of Education (MIE).</p>	<p>While COVID shutdowns did delay our work, we were able to deliver our initial book production for milestone 2 and 3 deliverables during lock down. While not ideal for startup, we were able to move our planned in person new title development training to a remote workshop effectively.</p> <p>Working remotely did force us to develop some tools that would be useful in any context, including translation templates. The ACR storybook concept template was also very helpful.</p>
<p>Some translations and spelling in Citumbuka are not standardized. We received feedback throughout the project that some words were not correctly translated or were misspelled.</p>	<p>We standardized on the translations and spelling recommended by the colleagues we engaged from the University of Malawi. These are somewhat “academic” but we needed to choose one standard. MIE also uses the University of Malawi spellings for their content.</p>

<p>Copyright: We sourced two books in the Cat and Dog series by Elke and Rene Leisink sourced from African Storybook. The African Storybook versions are clearly marked with Creative Commons Licensing.</p> <p>We were unaware of the licensing issue until another BWB awardee was contacted by the authors, who claim not to have given permission for CC licensing for re-use.</p> <p>We had already translated and produced two books from this series to accessible EPUB with MSL videos. As a result, we needed to produce two additional books with MSL videos which had a time and budget implication. We have followed up to inform African Storybook of the issue. The Asia Foundation's BWB team is in touch with the authors, as they also experienced the copyright issue.</p> <p>A more general challenge exists in that, in all cases, we are trusting that CC licensing on source materials is correct. Often these materials have already been adapted from an original source, sometimes only using illustrations or character concepts, any of which could be legitimately copyrighted.</p>	<p>Creative Commons sources should be verified through contacting the original creator of the work, though on some books the original creator's contact is lost or dropped.</p> <p>Producers of CC content should consider adding a licensing contact for reuse of CC BY materials. We are often starting with a title that has already been adapted several times or includes CC illustrations with new text. ACR and others should consider updating their title page requirements to include a licensing contact. eKitabu will certainly make this change going forward for new CC BY materials we produce.</p>
<p>We were unable to adapt the books developed by the USAID Malawi Early Grade Reading Improvement Activity (MERIT) as they were produced prior to USAID's mandate that all TLM should have CC licensing. After reviewing all of the MERIT books, we did find that 18 were sourced from Creative Commons works, which we then adapted and translated into Citumbuka.</p>	<p>More recent USAID contracts require materials developed with USAID funding to be Creative Commons licensed, so this issue should not occur going forward. However, past materials may not be able to be adapted.</p> <p>It is very difficult for awardees to navigate past project agreements between USAID, an implementing partner and</p>

	a government agency that claims copyright to materials developed under USAID awards.
MSL video production challenges	
<p>Many of the challenges related to MSL video production were caused by gaps in the time the videos were produced, then edited and QA'd. Second takes, or new edits introduced <i>new</i> quality issues requiring more rounds of QA and rework.</p>	<p>These gaps had various causes (power, staffing, Internet). However, we propose a singular solution in response to these challenges, namely a distinct budget allocation for a consistent local core team staff, that has local sign language skills, along with video editors.</p> <p>This may seem to cause a slower production schedule to start, but will pay off over time in more efficient production. The ideal is a steady core team. In every country where we have started local sign language video production, there has been some natural turnover in staffing, due to skills and everyday life circumstances.</p> <p>A realistic time frame is 2 years to build and train a core team. Great work, and many books, can be done in this time, but projects should start out with a 2-year time horizon to build the team, with a vision to sustain the team beyond 2 years to achieve continued output.</p>
<p>OPD members often have other jobs, and cannot dedicate themselves to video production full time. This will be more of a constraint in smaller countries and smaller disability communities. OPD members need some assurance of a steady, long term income to leave their current employment and shift to content production.</p>	<p>See above recommendation about building a steady team with a 2-year time horizon. However, noting in many cases, there may not be a simple solution, even with a long time horizon.</p> <p>We continue to believe that accessible digital content production can be a viable career path for persons with</p>

	<p>disabilities, especially considering many of the core technologies—html, web design and video production—are in demand. This would need more focus and investment, as these skills often require several years of training and hands on learning for a person to provide services competitively.</p>
<p>Other commitments of video editors in Malawi. These video editors were contractors working on multiple contracts at one time, often with scheduling conflicts.</p> <p>There is a conflict between paying contractors per video/book, which results in rushed work and low incentives to re-do low quality work, and for their time (days, weeks) which may not be sufficient to finish the work.</p>	<p>See above. However, we recognize that many projects will not have the budget for full time video production staff over the long term.</p> <p>Most video editors - at least in Africa where eKitabu has worked - work as freelancers, earning income for conferences, weddings, commercials and occasional documentary work. These fees may seem quite high, but are justified given their irregular work and high cost of equipment.</p> <p>At the start up of a Sign Language Video Storybook project, it may not be cost effective to hire them full time - or at least is difficult to negotiate full time work given their standard “gig” rates.</p> <p>However, providing training to OPD members in video editing may shift or replace the editor role at start up with a full time training role for an experienced technical video editor. Taking a long term perspective and adding workforce development as an explicit project outcome may be able to smooth out and/increase budgets to resolve this challenge. It's worth noting that learning these skills requires hands-on, “apprenticeship” type learning, which a</p>

	Sign Language Video Storybook project could provide over time.
Understanding of instructions by video editors. Editors lacked knowledge in MSL, causing communication challenges and incorrect work that needed to be redone, at times required re-shooting original video.	See above—we believe training OPDs in video production is a good solution, albeit one that requires a long time and budget commitment. Editing sign language video storybooks is a very specific skill, and while the general technical aspects of video production are transferable, many sign language video storybook guidelines are not intuitive for video editors new to the process.
Based on feedback from MANAD, we changed our original plan of using Citumbuka as a base language to producing 40 books with Chichewa text and audio + MSL and 10 books with Citumbuka text and audio +MSL. The vast majority of learners who are deaf in Malawi are using Chichewa as their written language for literacy instruction.	Consult local OPDs on language choice issues. Working with ACR and MANAD we believe we arrived at the right compromise of a 40/10 mix of Chichewa and Citumbuka text for the 50 MSL video storybooks produced.
General EPUB production and adaptation challenges	
<p>Errors from early on in the production process - starting with copyediting (typos,punctuation, kerning and lack of title cases) errors in the original content were carried into translation and adaptation, then into EPUB programming.</p> <p>New punctuation and capitalization errors were also introduced in translation. eKitabu and ACR's final QA caught these errors, but only at the end of the production process. Thank you Erin and Sonny for your continued QA.</p>	All Creative Commons sourced content should be copy edited before adaptation. A second round of copy editing is required for translations. Having the accessibility tools for QA as part of the content development has been helpful to get content with 0 errors.

<p>Leveling schemes: The leveling scheme set out in the initial BWB competition materials was not the same as the GDL's <i>current</i> scheme. This may have changed just before the start of our work. We needed to re-level many books, which caused re-work cascading through our metadata, title pages and cover images in the EPUBs.</p>	<p>We recommend ACR, GDL and others name and version their leveling schemas. We recognize a universal leveling schema is probably not realistic, and that projects will always need different leveling. Given that fact, naming the schema “ACR version 2” “GDL version 3” could help map between schemas and make reuse and adaptation easier for others in the future.</p>
<p>Names for languages with different spelling conventions. The translators had different opinions and preferences.</p>	<p>The preferred terms for the languages as advised by the translators are: Ciyawo, Ellomwe, and Citumbuka.</p>
<p>New content development</p>	
<p>Most authors and publishers we have worked with in Malawi have not been trained to develop early grade books. This is primarily the responsibility of the MIE.</p> <p>Authors found it challenging to create first drafts of the new storybooks, with limited examples in local languages to serve as a guide. First drafts were inadvertently focused on highlighting negative perceptions about persons with disabilities and making this the central theme of the story rather than incorporating protagonists with disabilities in a representative and positive/natural manner.</p> <p>Another challenge was fitting the books into the length and word choice / vocabulary for the early grade reading levels targeted in our project.</p>	<p>When we identified this gap, we added our colleague Helen Patuck—a phenomenal SEL specialist and renowned children’s storybook author and illustrator—into our creative process to support the Malawian authors and publishers contributing stories to the project.</p> <p>Helen participated in the May 2021 remote content development workshop, and then edited the books to include SEL activities and questions. She also provided feedback to the authors to guide them in character development. This was a very hands on, iterative process with the authors over a period of six months.</p> <p>We will budget for this type of resource going forward when engaging in new content development.</p>

4.0 Next steps, challenges and recommendations for future projects

As in Section 3, we pair each challenge in the table below with a next step or recommendation.

Challenge	Recommendation and/or Lesson Learned
Lack of ICT infrastructure and devices and newness of accessible digital content	
<p>As Sekerani Kufakwina of MANAD commented after our school visits in May 2022, this is the first time MSL video storybooks have been produced and introduced in Malawian schools.</p> <p>What can we learn about how best to introduce this new content, to support teachers, and to drive utilization and impact?</p>	<p>ACR is currently supporting MANAD through its sustainability fund through a small technical assistance award: supporting MANAD members to work directly with schools that serve Deaf children is the right first step to understand needs for teacher training and ongoing support to train teachers on how to use and integrate assistive technologies, devices, and SL video storybooks into classroom curriculum and reading instruction</p>
<p>The lack of power, connectivity, and devices are consistently cited as barriers to the adoption of accessible digital content and assistive technologies in Malawi. Our school visits confirmed that devices are not readily available. Makande Resource Centre had some devices, but they were not being utilized, nor were teachers in these schools supported with appropriate content and training.</p>	<p>Map ICT infrastructure and devices available in special needs schools and schools that serve children with disabilities, including the Resource Centers assisted by USAID REFAM.</p> <p>Survey education stakeholders and donors to identify devices and infrastructure that have been deployed. This mapping can inform future investments in ICT infrastructure, devices, content distribution, and maintenance plans.</p>
<p>Same as above, but specifically for Orbit Reader devices and other refreshable braille displays.</p> <p>Malawi Union of the Blind has distributed 253 devices over the past several years. These devices do not contain curriculum content.</p>	<p>As of August 2022, eKitabu is coordinating with MUB to distribute the BWB ebraille materials to all 253 devices. To date, we delivered a full set of titles to MUB and loaded 12 devices at Makande Resource Centre. We are developing a solution with MUB to distribute the materials to all of the devices, as this has been prioritized by the Director of Special Needs Education, Mrs. Lucy Magagula.</p>

	<p>eKitabu has talked with MUB in regards to getting all the e-braille materials loaded on the devices, however there are logistical challenges they face in traveling to the schools. MUB is to share a budget and work plan proposing how this will be accomplished.</p> <p>In addition to the above, support MOE DSNE in their request for help to ensure the Orbit Readers delivered in 2018 and 2019 are working, maintained, and provisioned with relevant content. This request was made by the DSNE Director in a meeting in May 2021.</p>
<p>Devices that have been deployed do not have appropriate content because of unavailability of accessible digital content at the time the devices were procured and distributed to learners.</p>	<p>Make BWB materials readily available online and offline. eKitabu will respond to any requests going forward from MIE if they can provide hosting and distribution for these materials. We also hope the GDL can add support for e-braille downloads. eKitabu continues to advocate for content distribution plans for any device procurement projects. Our staff will load content on devices whenever possible as they travel throughout Malawi on future projects.</p>
<p>Accessing the MSL Vocabulary Guide website developed under BWB requires an internet connection.</p>	<p>To design an offline version of the Vocabulary Guide, the first step is to investigate what types of devices are most readily available and what formats do they support, for example, an Android app, EPUB, USB, or DVD.</p>
<p>Limited capacity of teachers in special needs schools and Resource Centers to support learners with disabilities, including low levels of braille and MSL skills among teachers.</p>	<p>Engage with Malawian OPDs, particularly MANAD, MUB and FEDOMA to leverage, sustain and scale their efforts in and outside of the education system to build capacity for inclusion of children, parents, caregivers and teachers in language and literacy development. We understand that this is a priority for MOE and USAID.</p>
<p>Sustainable book & content development</p>	

MIE requested more support after the Accessible Digital Content Workshop to assist their understanding and development of accessible digital content.	eKitabu's team in Malawi will continue to engage with MIE to build capacity and collaborate in widening access and accessibility of Malawian learning content.
MIE requested support in distributing digital materials.	Engage with MIE to understand their needs and strategies for online and offline distribution of materials.
MIE expressed interest and support in distributing titles developed under BWB.	Coordinate with MIE to review the already developed books for approval and use in schools.
Several education sector projects have developed print and digital materials; however, it is hard to assess which materials exist and how leverageable they are for future work.	Investigate the current status and availability of past and present projects in the education sector, including Malawi's National Reading Program including copyright.
Local publishers and authors lack experience in developing early grade teaching and learning materials because of a lack of a market for these materials. "No demand, no supply."	Implement recommendations in the GBAIA Malawi Book Supply Chain Analysis report to address these systemic issues in the local book chain.
Lack of short-term opportunities for local publishers and authors to develop early grade reading materials without significant changes in procurement policy.	Incentivize Malawian publishers and MIE to produce born accessible digital content in a "Content Development Challenge" (the CDC was first launched in Kenya in 2018 under ACR Book Boost Access for All Challenge and successfully incentivized Kenyan publishers to develop 70 new, born accessible titles).
BWB milestones primarily focused on book <i>development</i> not <i>distribution</i> .	<p>Engaged and built capacity with colleagues from World Vision Malawi on how to use the app in their reading clubs program, with an aim of increasing access and driving utilization of the materials. 44,961 books printed by World Vision from BWB titles.</p> <p>Clear next step to make digital content available to government and other education stakeholders, and future USAID and other</p>

	donor funded projects. (eKitabu’s Malawian team is actively engaged in this now.)
Teacher Training and Lack of MSL Skills among teachers	
As noted above in our notes on the school visit, few teachers have been training, nor are proficient in MSL.	One of the ideas we discussed at Mountainview related to workforce development was for students matriculating to come back as auxiliary teachers for preschool/elementary classes. This would support work for persons with disabilities as well as support schools.

5.0 Project-level Indicator Progress

- End of Project [ITT submitted](#) update as of 30th August 2022
- MEL plan and ITT submitted 1st October 2020
- Piloting the SAT framework, submitted on 9th April 2021, update on 7th July 2021, updated on 9th August 2021
- Participated in CLA sessions 9th May 2021 and provided feedback requested by 11th June 2021
- Participated in the CLA session 13th December 2021
- Submitted the CLA survey on 5th May 2022

6.0 Photos and Annexes

Annex 1: Photos

- [MSL production with MANAD](#)
- [School Visit photos](#)
- [Accessible Digital Content Workshop](#)

eKitabu Studio KSL team, MANAD and Director, Department of Special Needs Education and Director of Teacher Education Training meeting in Lilongwe, Malawi

ACR team: Erin Williams, WVUS/GESI team: Edward Winter, World Vision Malawi: Thandeka Nkhonde; MANAD: Sekerani Kufakwina; eKitabu: Anna Martin, Mercy Kirui; Teachers and Learners at Mountain View School for the Deaf

MOE, MIE, USAID, ACR, OPDs, University of Malawi, Publishers & eKitabu representatives during the Accessible Digital Content Workshop in Blantyre, Malawi

Annex 2: Monthly Project Reports

Date	Link
June 2020	BWB Project report
July 2020	BWB Project report
August 2020	BWB Project report
September 2020	BWB Project report
October 2020	BWB Project report
November 2020	BWB Project report
December 2020	BWB Project report
January 2021	BWB Project report
February 2021	BWB Project report
March 2021	BWB Project report
April 2021	BWB Project report
May 2021	BWB Project report
June 2021	BWB Project report

Date	Link
July 2021	BWB Project report
August 2021	BWB Project report
September 2021	BWB Project report
October 2021	BWB Project report
November 2021	BWB Project report
December 2021	BWB Project report
January 2022	BWB Project report
February 2022	BWB Project report
March 2022	BWB Project report
April 2022	BWB Project report
June 2022	BWB Project report
July 2022	BWB Project report

Annex 3: [Work Plan](#)

Annex 4: Book List

- [Milestone 2 list](#)
- [Milestone 3 Book list](#)
- [Milestone 4 Book list](#)
- [Milestone 5 & 7 Book list - MSL list](#)
- [BWB Master Metadata Sheet](#)

Annex 5: BWB Accessible EPUBs

- [Milestone 2](#)
- [Milestone 3](#)
- [Milestone 4](#)
- [Milestone 5](#)
- [Milestone 7](#)

Annex 6: Communication

These are the key highlights in comms for the BWB project 2020 - 2022:

- [Feature on eKitabu D](#)
- [eKitabu Digital Storytime](#)
- [eKitabu BWB Project in Malawi](#)
- [Sign Language content for learners in Kenya](#)
- [Partner engagements in Malawi](#)
- [BWB Project Feature](#)
- [Newsletter Feature: International Week of Deaf People](#)
- [Talking with My Mum Book Feature from Malawi](#)
- [Draft Blogpost: Workshop with ACR & EdTech partners in Malawi](#)
- [Newsletter Feature on BWB project](#)
- We have also been working on comms activities as highlighted in the project [Comms Plan](#) for Milestones 5-8. The document shows a plan of the activities carried out, featuring the schedule and links to the stories.
- The table below is a summary of all activities done since the launch of the project in 2020.

Event Type	Date	Event	Venue
TV broadcast	15 Apr 2020 - present	eKitabu Digital Story Time	Kenya MOE EDU TV: Tuesdays - Fridays, 6:05 - 6:35PM

Blog post	28 Apr 2020	https://allchildrenreading.org/news/ekitabus-digital-story-time-brings-hope-to-out-of-school-children-a-cross-kenya-2/	ACR Blog
Blog post	06 May 2020	https://allchildrenreading.org/news/ekitabu-seeks-to-transform-the-production-of-quality-accessible-books-in-local-languages-of-africa/	ACR Blog
TV Interview	12 May 2020	Interview on Digital Story Time with Georgine Auma, eKitabu Studio KSL Director	Citizen TV, Kenya
eKitabu	12 May 2020	Digital Essay Competition soft launch - online	Nairobi, Kenya https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E6yAeFONuHM&list=PLfRU3c2GZU0s2BZRXSIfCs1Pr2QYVr9fD
eKitabu	26 May 2020	Digital Essay Competition official launch - Facebook live	Facebook Live

Webinar	04 Jun 2020, 9:30 AM EDT	<p>Webinar: Language before Literacy The importance of language acquisition and communication first approaches for Deaf and hard of hearing children, building the evidence base in Africa.</p> <p>eKitabu in cooperation with Deaf Child Worldwide, Royal Dutch Kentalis</p>	https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLfRU3c2GZU0tpOGzL1d3IRPgN7YRtdsWv
UN Habitat Conference	24 - 26 Jun 2020	<p>Private Sector Partnership Forum Innovative Solutions to Challenges in Slums & Informal Settlements in Africa</p>	Virtual
Ubongo Kids Webinar	25 Jun 2020	<p>Building Brains @ Home: What can we learn about learning from the COVID-19 crisis and beyond?</p>	Virtual
Mastercard Foundation EdTech Mondays	20 Jul 2020	<p>Parent (TEACH)ING: Navigating until January 2021</p>	Virtual

Mastercard Foundation Secondary Education Virtual Summit	13 Aug 2020	Preparing youth for the future of work	Virtual
Webinar	8 Sep 2020	Business of Books webinar with Julie Cram and Will Clurman on Global Literacy Day https://www.globalbookalliance.org/news-views/webinar-business-of-books-can-advance-literacy	Virtual
Blog post	11 Sep 2020	Pivoting in a Pandemic: eKitabu Provides Sign Language Video Content For Students https://www.edu-links.org/learning/pivoting-pandemic-ekitabu-provides-sign-language-video-content-students	ACR Blog
eKitabu	24 Sep 2020	Digital Essay Competition Prize Giving - online	https://youtu.be/tDpp78PwArg

KPA	24 - 26 Sep 2020	Nairobi International Book Fair	http://www.nairobiinternationalbookfair.org/
eKitabu	25 Sep 2020	Content Development Challenge Launch	Virtual
TV Interview	9 Oct 2020	Interview on the challenges of Deaf children while reporting back to school; with Georgine Auma, eKitabu Studio KSL Director	KTN News
eKitabu	29 Oct 2020	<p>Round table Discussion and Family of the Year Award (FOYA) Prizegiving</p> <p>https://www.ekitabu.com/2020/11/19/2020-family-of-the-year-award-foya-prizegiving/</p> <p>Inclusion in <i>Education</i>: Focus on families of children with disabilities at home and in school</p>	Virtual
Partner	25 Nov 2020	<p>Remote Learning Challenge Award Ceremony for 7,000 teachers and County Trainers with CEMASTE.A.</p> <p>Based on ICT utilization and innovation in a virtual classroom</p> <p>Remote Learning Challenge Event</p>	Virtual

Blog Post	2 Dec 2020	<p>Three Ways USAID is Supporting Persons with Disabilities to Face the Challenges of COVID-19</p> <p>https://medium.com/usaid-2030/three-ways-usaid-is-supporting-persons-with-disabilities-to-face-the-challenges-of-covid-19-4b4e86b89cdd</p>	Virtual
Blog Post	15 Dec	<p>Accessible to All: Creating Learning Materials for Children with Disabilities in Cambodia, Kenya, Rwanda, and Tajikistan</p> <p>https://www.edu-links.org/learning/accessible-learning-materials-children-disabilities-cambodia-kenya-rwanda-tajikistan</p>	Virtual
Blog Post	8 Jan 2021	<p>https://edtechhub.org/2021/01/08/using-innovative-methods-to-train-teachers-of-blind-children-what-we-learned/</p>	Blog Post
Edtech Hub	3 Feb 2021	<p>eKitabu, Learning Equality, and Rising Academies: Learnings from the Hub's Covid-19 grantees</p>	Virtual

eKitabu	17 - 19 Feb 2021	Regional Kickoff events for 2021 Digital Essay Competition (DEC) and Family of the Year Award (FOYA) Mombasa/Lamu counties	Schools: Likoni School for the Blind, Little Stars Academy, Jaffery Academy, Lamu County Education Office
eKitabu	23 - 26 Feb 2021	Regional Kickoff events for 2021 Digital Essay Competition (DEC) and Family of the Year Award (FOYA) Siaya/Kisumu/Vihiga/Bungoma counties	Schools: Ebukuya School for the Deaf - Vihiga, St. Oda School for the Visually Impaired - Siaya, Maranda High School- Siaya, St. Francis High Rangala Girls High school, Nina School for the Deaf, Maseno school for the Deaf, Kibos school for the Blind, Aluor Mixed Primary school
International Publishers Association/ African Publishing Innovation Fund	10 Mar 2021	African Publishing Innovation Fund to Improve Access to Education, Books, and Literacy Skills for 11 Million Young Africans	Press release

eKitabu	16 Mar 2021	Story Development Workshop with DPOs, WVI, J&A REFAM, authors, illustrators, teachers in Malawi	Virtual
eKitabu	17 Mar 2021	Story Development Workshop with DPOs, WVI, J&A REFAM, authors, illustrators, teachers in Malawi	Virtual
UNESCO	22 Apr 2021	The Future of Education for Persons with Disabilities	Virtual
eKitabu, Language Before Literacy	28 Apr 2021	CIES Presentation: A Comparative Perspective of Inclusive Education for Learners who are Deaf or Hard of Hearing in Africa	Virtual
eKitabu, All Children Reading	29 Apr 2021	CIES Presentation: Sign Language storybook TV broadcasts to enable continued literacy learning during COVID for children who are deaf	Virtual

All Children Reading	5 May 2021	Global Digital Development Forum (GDDF)	Virtual
International Disability and Development Consortium's (IDDC)	19 May 2021	International Disability and Development Consortium Accessible and Inclusive Education	Virtual
eKitabu, International Publishers Association (IPA), Kenya Publishers Association (KPA)	20 May 2021	2021 Content Development Challenge (CDC) Training with Kenyan publishers	Virtual
Kigali Public Library awards 18 winning	28 May 2021	https://www.ekitabu.com/2021/06/04/kigali-public-library-awards-18-winning-students-in-its-first-annual-writing-competition/	Kigali, Rwanda

students in its first Annual Writing Competition			
eKitabu Trip to Malawi	Jun/Jul 2021	Visit by eKitabu team to Malawi. Brief engagement with partner organizations and MIE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● USAID Malawi ● MIE ● DSNE/DTED ● World Vision ● MANAD eKitabu visit to Malawi Blogspot	Malawi
eKitabu, Storymoja Publishers	16 Jun 2021	eKitabu participates in the Storymoja Read Aloud event	Nairobi, Kenya

UNICEF	23 Jun 2021	eKitabu Digital Story Time	UNICEF Accessible Digital Learning Portal
ACR	23 Aug 2021	How ACR GCD innovators using EdTech adjusted to COVID-19 — and what lies ahead	ACR Newsletter & blog
International Week of the Deaf	20 - 26 Sep 2021	https://mailchi.mp/df26feb752b3/ekitabu-tunaenda-digital-newsletter-september-2021	eKitabu Tunaenda Digital September Newsletter
ACR featured Talking with My Mum book	23 Sep 2021	https://allchildrenreading.org/news/creation-of-sign-language-storybooks-expands-world-of-reading-and-storytime-to-deaf-children-and-their-families/	ACR Blog Post
mEducation Panel Presentation	28 Sep 2021	ACR Accessibility panel presentation hosted by Sergio Ramirez-Mena	Virtual
ACRU	27 -30 Sep	DRAFT Rwanda UDL Teacher Training Blog	Kigali Rwanda

DAISY Information Sharing Day	14 Oct	https://us02web.zoom.us/webinar/register/WN_D3WVPr2aQrglgUJ1behUmw	Virtual
ACRU	22 Nov	eKitabu launches teacher training to increase access and learning opportunities for children with disabilities in Rwanda	Kigali, Rwanda
eKitabu	02 Dec	Digital Essay Competition Official Prizegiving	Virtual
eKitabu	15 Dec	Family of the Year 2021 Prizegiving and Roundtable Discussion	Virtual
eKitabu/ACR	04 Jan 2022	Following up on use of Kenyan Sign Language materials created under Sign On for Literacy. We shared “stunning photos” with Sergio	Sergio Ramirez-Mena for Josh Josa of USAID on Link to photos
eKitabu/ HI	10 Jan 2022	Humanity & Inclusion approved Blogpost on eKitabu engagement with learners, teachers and caregivers in	Link to the blog

		Kakuma and Refugee Camps This post and photos can be widely shared.	
eKitabu	24 Jan 2022	January Tunaenda Digital Newsletter	eKitabu Newsletter
GBAIA	07 - 11 Mar 2022	Content Development Workshop with publishers	Malawi Sun Hotel, Blantyre
eKitabu/IPA	10 Mar	Content Development Challenge Prizegiving	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1D4vsjB7x_W_pqAZTdZBKlsc2xsH6ugXU/view?usp=sharing
IPA	21 - 24 Mar	Bologna Children's Bookfair Social media posts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facebook • Twitter • LinkedIn 	eKitabu presentation: Spotlight in Africa Publishing
eKitabu/ACR	24 - 27 May	Content Development Workshop using eKitabu EPUB Toolkit customized for Malawi	Blantyre, Malawi

		Link to draft blogpost - pending feedback from Carmen & Erin	
		<p>Links to digital media posts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Facebook: Post 1, Post 2, Post 3 ● Twitter: Tweet 1, Tweet 2, Tweet 3 ● LinkedIn: Post 1, Post 2, Post 3 ● Instagram: Post 1, Post 2, Post 3 	Blantyre, Malawi
eKitabu	Jun 2022	https://mailchi.mp/ekitabu/ekitabu-tunaenda-digital-newsletter-june-2022	eKitabu Tunaenda Digital Newsletter
eKitabu/ACR post event activities	18 Jul	<p>Links to digital media posts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Facebook ● Twitter ● LinkedIn ● Instagram 	GBAIA / EDC Workshop in Malawi
Strengthening Teacher Education Program (STEP) Work plan Coordination Workshop	STEP	Work plan Coordination Workshop	Crossroads Hotel, Lilongwe, Malawi